

SPECIFIC FEATURES AND RULES OF DRAMATURGY

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Abstract: This article describes what dramaturgy is, its unique features and advantages, and its rules.

Key words: classical method, Aristotle, two sides of dramaturgy, Bronislav Nushic, "Unedited thoughts",

In the explanatory dictionary of the Uzbek language, "dramaturgy is a dramatic art; the theory of the principles and methods of the structure of the stage work", it is said in the national encyclopedia of Uzbekistan, "dramaturgy is a complex of dramatic works; the concept of figurative interpretation of cinema and performances". Dramaturgy is the written basis of stage art, and as a type of creativity, it is not only related to words, but also has other art characteristics. That is why it is a complex art. Dramaturgy has several stage requirements, and all of them, i.e. words, movement, music, architecture, painting and sculpture play an important role.

One of the most important conditions and foundations of dramaturgy is the expression of vitality, truthfulness and artistic perfection in a smooth, synthetic way, at the level of skill. Not only the playwright, the director is responsible for fulfilling these two requirements on the stage fully and skillfully, but also the actor, artist, even the lamp master, the electrician who creates the color image, who participates in preparing this work and delivering it to the audience. it's slow.

The second basis: the authenticity and vitality of the conflict in the drama includes the issue of the ability to organize drama.

The third basis: drama is the skill of creating action, its organization and subjugation. Dramatic action is the originality and aesthetic feature of a stage play, drama, and is the lifeblood of the performance. This factor has a great place and importance in the success of the play. Action is not only a physical effort, walking, running, but a complex of mental states, which includes monologues, dialogues, gestures, speechless situations, facial expressions, intonation, remarks, pantomimes. After all, the dramatic action serves as the lifeblood of the performance in order to preserve and fully express the integral integrity of the drama.

The fourth principle is to create a character in a drama. Because understanding of the world, nature, universe, man, being, understanding of reality and artistic expression is realized by creating an image - a character. After all, since the main source of literature is man, the more artistically perfect his image and character are, the more effective the ideological-artistic aesthetic goal of the work will be. Because of this, character creation is important as the leading factor of humanities and the main sign of dramaturgy.

The fifth principle: The successful implementation of plot and composition in drama is closely related. In the same way that the thoroughness of the main project is considered important for the building, building, house to be compact, comfortable, bright and cozy for a person, the more thorough the plot and composition of the drama is, the greater is the idea of the work and its educational and educational value. it works. After all, the need to organize and implement the plot and composition is also an important factor in dramaturgy.

The sixth principle: Achieving the goal, quality mark, feature. That is, it is to achieve and express the mutual, basic feature of forms such as comedy, tragedy (tragedy), drama.

The seventh principle: Drama, like any kind of artistic work, requires language and speech skills. Moreover, it is necessary to skillfully use the

possibilities of monologue and dialogue. It differs from other literary genres by the same feature.

The eighth principle: the place and role of remark in a drama. To be able to organize and implement these main characters on the stage (as a director, actor, artist) in a whole, organically, and perfectly. and requires high artistic implementation. Of course, in addition to the qualities and signs that we have listed, there may be many more main signs. It is necessary to fill up according to the skills, knowledge, level and experience of the teacher teaching this subject.

The social, spiritual, educational, educational and ideological responsibility of the author of the play is incomparable. Because the idea in the play is intended to be conveyed to the audience through the stage. The director and actors, who bring it to life, are influenced by the author's idea, in the given conditions, embody the thoughts of the characters in the characters, and move them in the system of events.

An artist who writes a work for the stage must first of all be aware of the complex technology of the theater, i.e. the production process, the rules of the stage art and the means of expression. Only then will the stage work have the power of a correctly expressed artistic thought, the vitality that can attract the attention of the audience, the system of bright events and the development of logical struggles and their solution. When the author places the fate of his characters in the system of events, he moves them according to the purpose in the characters that serve to reveal the idea of the work, and vividly expresses the contradictions and struggles that occur in the pursuit of each character's goal. This aspiration and struggle turns the audience into a participant of the event, interests, excites, and sometimes makes them laugh or cry.

When it comes to the construction of a stage work in an artistic form, in the rule introduced by Aristotle, passed down from century to century, recognized as the "classical method" - "great error, difficulty, realization, peripetia, that is, a sharp turn, pathos, or "is a logical system such as the unfolding of passions and

solution". As an example of this, world theater scholars point to the works of Shakespeare and Moliere, and Russians to the dramaturgy of Pushkin, Gogol, Ostrovsky and Chekhov. It is possible to see that in their stage works, the main features of artistry have been mastered in various forms and have a common system. Great dramatists created exemplary works because they mastered the "classical method" and were able to explain their theoretical ideas about theater art. A. Chekhov believes that it is possible to determine their common artistic features by comparing exemplary works of different eras. It is possible to understand the generality of the definition. This generality should be accepted as laws and regulations. There is a generality in immortal works. If the common aspects are removed from them, the work loses its artistic value and charm," he says. Therefore, general rules and "classical method" are a necessary condition for a work claiming immortality.

There is no success without the unity of the two sides of dramaturgy - the art of words and the art of the stage. Because drama belongs to the art of words on the one hand, and on the other hand, it fully complies with the rules of theater art. It requires that it be created as a sample. The characteristic feature of the drama is that the author becomes a direct mediator between the audience and his characters, and thus it is natural for him to express his attitude to the important and topical issues of the time. A stage play must be created as an artistic whole, preserving the "integrity of dramatic action". So, movement is important in drama. In it, the expression of characters through movement ensures the stageness of the play. Events escalate and "explode" and have a solution. As an example, we can show Uzbek classic works such as "Boy ila servantchi", "Alisher Navoi".

Chernyshevsky, who read Aristotle's "Poetics", said that one cannot create a theory of a thing without studying its history. Without a theory of a thing, it is impossible to comment on its history. Because this leads to the conclusion that the significance and limits of history cannot be defined without theory.

Sharp conflicts and struggles in dramaturgy discover a special meaning in different circumstances, characteristic of the author's interpretation. That's why Stanislavsky defines the point of reference for an actor as appropriate, active and productive movement in the given conditions. In fact, the type of action changes with the change of conditions on the stage. But the goal may not change. Failure to take into account the conditions leads to imitation and the return of previous patterns. Stanislavsky was one of the first to realize this. In dramaturgy, it directs both the plot of the work and the development of the struggle between characters.

At the end of his life, Bronislav Nushich (1864-1938) kept a notebook in which he wrote down his thoughts on creativity and theater art and called them "Unedited Thoughts". These letters were published in "Teatr" magazine. At the end of these writings, he wrote twelve paragraphs of fertilizer for future playwrights and theater artists. I would like to draw your attention to these points below:

1. Don't write just because you want to write. Look for the factors that create the work - an idea, a thought, a fable, and let the idea behind the events and incidents in your life and the events that appear in your imagination inspire you to write.

2. Do not be fooled by the idea of the work with its charm, if you do not have the vision to finish the work you have started and your creative capabilities do not require it, it is better not to start that work. I have often regretted that I did not act on these ideas and abandoned the idea and content of the future work, admitting the fact that it does not correspond to my creative position. I found strength in myself.

3. Do not start writing until the thoughts and ideas of the play have reached their maturity and clearly formed in your imagination.

4. In order to build a building, it is necessary to strictly follow all the rules of architecture, so the demand in drama is similar. It also resembles a building with a foundation, floors, roof, and rooms. All its parts must be clearly and unambiguously connected with each other. There should be enough light in each

room, using every space there properly, and the number of rooms should be determined based on a logical basis. In dramaturgy, as in architecture, there are two laws:

a) it is necessary to create the external appearance of the building only after determining the internal structure of the building. In addition to the external and internal appearance of the building, its layout should also be determined based on its function.

b) in architecture, it is necessary to strictly follow the requirements of the size of the volumes in relation to each other. In terms of size, additionally, that is, auxiliary rooms must not be higher than the main rooms and wider than the floors above.

5. Do not invent anything on purpose. The stage cannot "digest" artificial and fake actions. Place them in such a way that one serves as a continuation of the other. Even an episodic event should have its own reason and be based on naturalness. Artistic integrity on stage can be achieved only through the logical coherence of events and events.

6. As an author, do not make it a condition that the actors follow your thoughts and opinions. It should not be felt that you are participating in your work. If I say it differently, in the process of writing, let your characters take place in your heart, and you only express their thoughts.

7. Don't overdo sentences and dialogues, they shouldn't be too silent. When the people on the stage speak, they should speak as they do in real life, so that it is not noticeable that they were written in advance by the author and memorized by the actors, and they should leave the impression that they are playing for the first time in the eyes of the audience.

8. Focus all your attention on the main character and do not look superficially at the secondary characters. Secondary characters also have their own character and have their own tasks.

9. In drama, just like in life events, there should be exposition, knot, development, climax and solution. Playwrights who are masters of their work know that this ratio is not the same size. For example, the distance between the node and the climax should be shorter. As soon as the solution of the play begins to appear, this problem should be solved. It is necessary to hurry, otherwise the viewer may "solve" this problem before the author.

10. Read your work aloud. You must understand the difference between the impression you read aloud and the impression you read in your mind. When you read aloud, you hear the impact of the words yourself. They may not even notice.

11. Don't rush to hear praise before reading your work. Do not ignore even the most trivial advice. It is better to think thoroughly and comprehensively than to object to the stated defects even when they seem insignificant.

12. Do not be intolerant of criticism. Even if the feedback is positive, don't take it as a support for your defense, and if it's negative, don't take it as your final judgment. Most importantly, consider each of your new works as my first work.

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